

A Re-Examination of Attention Deficit Disorder: Inattention, Distractibility, Sluggishness and Concentration Deficit

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Abstract

Attention deficit disorder (ADD) has always been considered as one of the three subtypes in the classical nosology of attention deficit-hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). Though ADD shares the same key triad of traits of ADHD, it does not fit exactly into the prescriptive (criterion-based traits) definition of ADHD but closer to the descriptive (observable traits) definition of the condition. Closer to ADD is the concentration deficit disorder (CDD), also known as Sluggish Cognitive Tempo (SCT), that has always been ignored in the literature of disabilities and disorders. With the introduction of the concept of Variable Attention Stimulus Trait (VAST) by Hallowell and Ratey (2021), the focus is now shifting to the variation of attention on a continuum rather than treating the deficit of attention in a staccato manner. In this short paper, the authors re-examined the condition of ADD by reviewing four associative concepts that are associated with it: inattention and distractibility, sluggishness and concentration.

Key Words: Attention, Concentration, Distractibility, Hyperactivity, Impulsivity, Inattention, Sluggishness

A Brief Introduction to Attention Deficit-Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) & its Subtypes

Attention Deficit-Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) was first identified in 1902 by a British pediatrician, Sir George Still, as an abnormal defect observed in children's moral control that caused poor control of their behavior despite their average and/or above intellectual capacity (see Holland, 2021; Lange et al., 2010, for detail). However, the condition did not attract serious attention of the professionals until the late 20th century when the American Psychiatric Association formally recognized ADHD as a mental

disorder, whose hallmarks are excessive amounts of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity. Also known as the triad of impairments in ADHD, these symptoms are pervasive, impairing in multiple contexts, and otherwise age-inappropriate.

The three key core/primary symptoms (also known as the triad of traits or TOTs for short) of ADHD – inattention, hyperactivity and impulsivity – constitute the classical nosography of the condition shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Triad of Traits in ADHD

Table 1 below shows the five categories of symptoms with a slight modification made to Pennington’s (1991) table of symptoms of ADHD,

including an addition of the idiopathic symptoms to define the nosology of ADHD.

Table 1. Symptomatological Classification of ADHD Traits

Core Symptoms	Correlated Symptoms	Secondary Symptoms	Artifactual Symptoms	Idiopathic Symptoms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inattention • Hyperactivity • Impulsivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sleep disturbance • Emotional lability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor self-esteem • Poor social skills • Academic problems • Substance abuse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety • Giftedness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct Disorder • Dyslexia

As a result, in the previous edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fourth Edition (DSM-IV-TR; American Psychiatric Association/APA, 2004), the TOTs was used to classify the disorder as three subtypes of ADHD (see Ohwovoriole, 2022, para. 5a, 5b & 5c), and each of the subtypes will be briefly described as follows:

- (1) Predominantly inattentive ADHD (also previously known as Attention Deficit Disorder or ADD), whose TOTs consists of forgetfulness, disorganization, and lack of focus.
- (2) Predominantly hyperactive-impulsive ADHD (ADHD-H/I), whose ToTs consists of restlessness and impulsive decisions, but not inattention.
- (3) Combined ADHD (ADHD-COM), whose ToTs consists of inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsivity.

• ADHD Subtype 1

Individuals (both children and adults) with ADD constitute the first subtype of ADHD. They do not show any signs of hyperactivity or impulsivity. Their key challenging issue of concern is the tendency to manifest difficulty in maintaining focus and/or to stay attentive. In other words, individuals

with ADD have to put in effort to pay more attention in order to stay on-task or to engage in organized activities for a long duration or period of time (Ohwovoriole, 2022, para. 6). Some of behavioral traits exhibited by individuals with ADD include the following, as listed by Ohwovoriole (2022; see para. 7): (1) Having short or poor attention span; (2) Easily to become distracted; (3) Inability to pay close attention to details; (4) Difficulty listening when being spoken to; (5) Forgetfulness is noted while performing everyday activities; (6) Exhibiting frequent carelessness in work/assignment done; (7) Constantly losing things like keys, books, and phones; (8) Struggling to engage in organized tasks and activities; and (9) Difficulty in following instructions. In addition, the authors have also observed and taken note of sluggishness observed in many individuals with ADD. The term Sluggish Cognitive Tempo (SCT) has been floating in the ADHD literature though not officially recognized for quite sometimes, and it refers to a syndrome related to ADHD but distinct from it (see Barkley, 2014, 2019). Its typical ToTs include the following: (1) Prominent dreaminess; (2) Mental fogginess; (3) Hypoactivity; (4) Sluggishness; (5) Staring frequently; (6) Inconsistent alertness; and (7) Exhibiting a slow working speed (Brooks, 2014; Silva, 2015).

Table 2. Symptomatological Classification of ADD Traits

Core Symptoms	Correlated Symptoms	Secondary Symptoms	Artifactual Symptoms	Idiopathic Symptoms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short attention • Distractibility • Sluggishness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypofocus • Poor working memory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to pay close attention to details • Difficulty listening when being spoken to • Difficulty in following instructions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forgetfulness • Stress disorder • Executive dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insomnia • Cognitive fatigue syndrome

ADHD Subtype II

Individuals with ADHD/HI constitute the second subtype of ADHD and they clearly exhibit hyperactive and impulsive behaviors. However, they show no symptoms of inattention. Such individuals are constantly on the move and often fidget excessively. Moreover, they are often quite disruptive in their behavior. This second subtype is typically characterized by the following behavioral traits of impulsivity as listed by Ohwovoriolè (2022, para. 9): (1) Interruption or intrusion of others’

privacy or social space; (2) Unintentional action without thinking through; (3) Impatience and with difficulty awaiting one’s turn; and (4) Blurting out answer to question asked before the speaker can completed it. In addition, behavioral traits of hyperactivity usually include the following listed by Ohwovoriolè (2022, para. 11) (see Table 3): (1) Restlessness; (2) Excessively talkative (hyperverbality); (3) Inability to focus on one task at a time; (4) Excessive fidgeting; and (5) Inability to engage in any activities quietly (National Institute of Mental Health, 2019).

Table 3. Symptomatological Classification of ADHD/HI Traits

Core Symptoms	Correlated Symptoms	Secondary Symptoms	Artifactual Symptoms	Idiopathic Symptoms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyperactivity • Impulsivity • Disruptiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyperverbality • Underlying mental & physical ill health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restlessness • Inability to focus on one task at a time • Excessive fidgeting • Inability to engage in any activities quietly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety • Giftedness • Hyperkinesia • Emotional dysregulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyperthyroidism • Brain disorders • Nervous system disorders • Psychological disorders

ADHD Subtype III

Finally, the third subtype of ADHD is manifested by individuals with ADHD-COM and they experience

a combination of all the key classical ToTs: (1) Inattention; (2) Hyperactivity; and (3) Impulsivity (see Figure 2) and in addition, sluggishness and disruptiveness (see Table 4).

Figure 2. The Model of the 3 ADHD Subtypes

Table 4 below shows the combination of all the symptoms from ADD and ADHD/HI to constitute ADHD-COM.

Table 4. Symptomatological Classification of ADHD-COM Traits

Core Symptoms	Correlated Symptoms	Secondary Symptoms	Artifactual Symptoms	Idiopathic Symptoms
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short attention • Distractibility • Sluggishness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypofocus • Poor working memory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inability to pay close attention to details • Difficulty listening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forgetfulness • Stress disorder • Executive dysfunction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insomnia • Cognitive fatigue syndrome

			when being spoken to		
			• Difficulty in following instructions		
• Hyperactivity	• Hyperverbality	• Restlessness	• Giftedness	• Hyperthyroidism	
• Impulsivity	• Underlying mental & physical ill health	• Inability to focus on one task at a time	• Hyperkinesia	• Brain disorders	
• Disruptiveness		• Excessive fidgeting	• Emotional dysregulation	• Nervous system disorders	
		• Inability to engage in any activities quietly		• Psychological disorders	

In assessing if someone has ADHD, the person suspected to suffer from the condition is required to show six or more symptoms of inattention and six or more symptoms of hyperactivity/impulsivity for at least a period of six months or more as stipulated in the DSM-5 (APA, 2013). In addition, those who are 17 years-old or more are required to show presence of five or more of each ToTs (APA, 2013).

Today with the publication of the fifth edition of the current DSM (DSM-5; APA, 2013), instead of using subtypes of ADHD, the term “presentations” has been used to describe the three manifestations of ADHD.

More than the Classical Nosology of ADHD

The term *nosology* (from Ancient Greek νόσος (*nosos*) 'disease', and -λογία (*-logia*) 'study of') refers to a specialized branch of medical science that deals with the classification of diseases. In the field of educational therapy, for instance, within the educological context, fully classifying a psychoeducational condition requires knowing its cause or a set of causes, the effects it has on the patient/client, the symptoms that are produced, and other issues or factors of concern, say for the challenging condition of ADHD. Depending on the choice of nosological classification system used, ADHD is placed under different diagnostic categories.

One good example of a nosological classification system is the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-Fifth Edition (DSM-5; APA, 2013) widely used by medical professionals and psychologists. In the new DSM-5, the three subtypes of ADHD are no longer in use but come under one type with two other categories as follows:

1. Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder
2. Other Specified Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder
3. Unspecified Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder

The International Classification of Diseases, Tenth Revision, Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM) published by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2015) is another globally used nosological classification system to provide diagnostic codes for classifying diseases. Interestingly, the ICD-10-CM does not formally recognize ADHD. However, the nosological classification system still includes the condition in the diagnostic criteria for hyperkinetic disorder (HKD), which is primarily defined as inattention and overactivity. Its diagnostic codes used for ADHD are as follows:

- F90.0, Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, predominantly inattentive type
- F90.1, Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, predominantly hyperactive type
- F90.2, Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, combined type
- F90.8, Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, other type
- F90.9, Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder, unspecified type

In the most recently released 11th edition of the ICD (ICD-11; World Health Organization, 2022) that has been adopted into clinical use, the term ADHD is used to replace the obsolete diagnostic label HKD. The WHO nosological classification system has also shifted to clustering neurodevelopmental disorders. Unlike the previous edition, the ICD-11 now recognizes ADHD subtypes including predominantly inattentive (ADD), predominantly hyperactive-impulsive (ADHD/HI), or combined (ADHD-COM) type.

The updated ICD-11 diagnostic codes for ADHD include the following:

- 6A05.Z Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, presentation unspecified
- 6A05.2 Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, combined presentation
- 6A05.Y Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, other specified presentation

6A05.0 Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, predominantly inattentive presentation

6A05.1 Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, predominantly hyperactive-impulsive presentation

A third example is the Educator's Diagnostic Manual of Disabilities and Disorders (Pierangelo & Guiliani, 2007) used by educators and educational therapists. The ADHD is placed under the Level 1 EDM Code OHI, which is Other Health Impairments. The condition falls under Level 2 EDM Code OHI-8.00 without any further subtypes.

The term *nosography* which differs from the earlier term *nosology*, is defined a description whose primary purpose is enabling a diagnostic label to be put on the situation. It outlines provisional and

conventional traits of a disability or disorder (also of a syndrome when two or more disabilities or disorders overlap or share their symptoms). As a result, nosography serves the goal of establishing an empirical diagnosis. According to Stanghellini and Fuchs (2013), the aim of nosography is to provide the description of single illnesses to allow their diagnosis. As such, a nosographical entity does need not have a single cause. For example, inability to stay attentive during a task to be engaged until completion due to poor or weak attention span and a difficulty for someone to refrain from being easily distracted or show a sluggish attitude toward a given task could be nosologically different but nosographically the same for that condition of ADHD (see Figure 3 below).

Figure 3. Nosographical Representation of ADHD with its 3 Subtypes

The authors of this paper feel strongly that the subtypes of ADHD should remain as what they are in the 'splitting' stance rather than taking the 'lumping' stance to put the subtypes under one broad type. The concept of 'lumping and splitting' refers to the process of determining a disability or disorder entity, specific (or per se) or spectrum (or continuum), as applied in the diagnostic evaluation of a condition, and in this case, ADHD. The 'splitters' and the 'lumpers' have fundamentally different approaches to psychoeducational diagnosis

and classification of disabilities and disorders (e.g., DSM, ICD, and EDM).

- Lumpers, on the one hand, point to the similarities *between* the diagnostic categories, and suggest that these similarities justify the creation of broader entities. Lumping stance serves to put in an indiscriminate mass or group or to treat as alike without regard for particulars (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Lumping Stance for ADHD

- Splitters, on the other hand, emphasize the heterogeneity within the diagnostic categories and argue that this heterogeneity drives the ‘splitting’ process. Splitting stance refers to the action of dividing or being divided into parts (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Splitting Stance for ADHD

Inattention versus Distractibility

Two interesting terms related to ADD are *inattention* and *distractibility*. According to Osen-Foss (2023), there is a difference between inattention and distractibility despite the fact that both go hand-in-hand and appear to be synonymous. However, they do not describe the same condition.

Stöppler (2019) defined “[I]nattention is the lack of focus when focus on a given event or situation is required” (para. 1). It is one of the classical hallmarks of ADD as well as ADHD-COM. “Children who are inattentive are often described as distracted ... kids who are distracted are often described as having trouble paying attention” (Osen-Foss, 2023, para. 1). Literally speaking, inattentive children simply cannot pay attention. It is as simple as that, and both parents and educators often use words to describe such children: “careless, neglectful, absent-minded, or day-dreaming” (Osen-Foss, 2023, para. 2). This can be described as being less mindful or aware of what is happening with one self or around oneself.

However, Hallowell and Ratey (2021) argued that the issue of inattention is not about attention deficit per se but is best understood in terms of the degree of variation in attention on a continuum. They coined the term *Variable Attention Stimulus Trait* (VAST) which they argued is a more representative name for ADHD. According to Hallowell and Ratey (2022), “ADHD is not purely a disorder; it is a mix of assets and liabilities” (para. 1). The Hallowell-Ratey model of ADHD recognizes the phenomenon of Rejection Sensitive Dysphoria (RSD) and its reverse side is the occurrence of Recognition Responsive Euphoria (RRE), which is “the super-charged response to perceived encouragement” (Hallowell & Ratey, 2022, para. 1).

Generally, the symptoms relating to inattention include the following: (1) Restlessness; (2) Problems performing tasks quietly; (3) Problems with executive functions such as planning, organizing, initiating and inhibiting; (4) Excessive talking; (5) Fidgeting; (6) Distractions; (7) Emotional liability that may include stress and anxiety; (8) Conflict and anger; and (9) Mood

change. According to Stöppler (2019), “[I]nattention can also be related to medical problems that interfere with an individual's cognitive function, such as stroke or dementia” (para. 1).

The other term is *distractibility*, which Sam (2023), in the Psychology Dictionary, defined it as “[H]aving difficulty in maintaining attention or being easily diverted away from an activity” (para. 1), and it is often observed in children with ADHD. Osen-Foss (2023) referred distractibility “to kids who can begin to focus on an activity but often quickly lose focus. Their attention is easily shifted. They get distracted by outside stimuli or even by their own thoughts. Often inattention can be the consequence of being distracted” (para. 3).

Sluggishness versus Concentration

Another two terms related to ADD are *sluggishness* and *concentration*. The dictionary meaning of *sluggishness* means “displaying little movement or activity; slow; inactive; lacking alertness, vigor, or energy; inert or indolent; slow to perform or respond to stimulation” (Free Dictionary, 2023, para. 1). The term is closely related to another condition known as Sluggish Cognitive Tempo (Barkley, 2014, 2019), but it is different from the condition of ADD.

There is another term that is associated with fatigue and sluggishness or sleepiness, and that is *lethargy*. “This sluggishness may be physical or mental ... these symptoms are described as lethargic. Lethargy can be related to an underlying physical or mental condition” (Nall, 2019, para. 1-2). Several studies (e.g., Kurtz, 2008; Salend & Rohena, 2003; Serman, 2000) have shown that many children with ADD manifest under-responsive attention systems, and are observed to be lethargic and slow to respond to learning challenges. The symptoms of lethargy include the following: (1) Mood change; (2) Decreased alertness or awareness; (3) Decreased ability to think or reason; (4) Fatigue or tiredness; (5) Low energy; and (6) Sluggishness. As a result, those who often feel lethargic “may act as if they are in a daze ... may move more slowly than usual” (Nall, 2019, para. 3).

The term *concentration* refers to the mental ability that an individual can focus on a single thought or task by directing all attention to it. Such an ability is best understood on a continuum between two extreme poles: hyperfocus and hypofocus. In between the two poles is what the authors have termed *ambifocus*, whose prefix *ambi* means ‘around or on both sides’. The term *hyperfocus* refers to an intense mental concentration of the conscious mind on a given subject, topic or task, and at times can result in side-tracking away from an assigned activity. It is often considered as the trait of

inattention seen in individuals with ADD. Moreover, hyperfocus is also a trait seen in other conditions such as schizophrenia and autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (Kooij et al., 2019; Webb et al., 2005). Ashinoff and Abu-Akel (2021) explained hyperfocus as “a phenomenon that reflects one’s complete absorption in a task, to a point where a person appears to completely ignore or tune out everything else” (p. 1) and is observed most in the context of ADHD, ASD and schizophrenia. The term *hypofocus* refers to limited or low concentration but is rarely mentioned in literature, and is the opposite of hyperfocus.

Where concentration deficit is the main issue of concern, there is another type of disorder known as Concentration Deficit Disorder (CDD) to be contended with. Known initially as Sluggish Cognitive Tempo (SCT) in the 1960s, its symptoms appear to be similar to ADD and were first systematically described in 1775 by a German physician and philosopher, Melchior Adam Weikard (b.1743-d.1803), and again in 1798 by a Scottish physician, Alexander Crichton (b.1763-d.1856), in their respective medical textbooks. However, Crichton (1798/2008) did not further describe any symptoms of the disorder, making this an early but certainly non-specific reference to an SCT-like syndrome (see Barkley, 2015, for detail), which has recently come under closer scrutiny.

Both SCT and CCD refer to the same condition by different names. Its symptoms can be easily mistaken for those of ADD. Lee et al. (2014) listed 10 key symptoms that are used to define individuals with SCT/CDD: “(1) daydreams; (2) attention fluctuates; (3) absent-minded; (4) loses train of thought; (5) easily confused; (6) seems drowsy; (7) thinking is slow; (8) slow-moving; (9) low initiative; and (10) easily bored, needs stimulation” (p. 8). In addition, individuals with SCT/CCD appear easily confused and dreamy or suffer from what is known as mental fog, which is also known as brain fog or clouding of consciousness (CoC), characterized by confusion, forgetfulness, lacking focus and poor mental clarity, and they often need extra time to complete given tasks. Social withdrawal and slow information processing are other potential symptoms of SCT/CDD.

Conclusion

The authors of this paper felt that it is too early to drop the term ADD from the current diagnostic manuals as the condition is not fully understood, properly explained or thoroughly investigated. The other associating conditions such as SCT, CCD or CoC are also not completely studied. The respective nosologies and nosographies of ADD, SCT or CCD remain unclear or ambiguous. Though some of the symptoms among these conditions are similar, more

research is still needed in this area of interest before any definitive conclusions about these analogous disorders can be established.

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